

The “Howness” Of Language As A Means Towards National Integration In Selected Nigerian Newspapers

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Abstract

Language is the prerogative of every human being and its primary function is communication. The use of language for effective communication has been taken for granted and this has resulted sometimes to conflict situations. Integration whether at the local, state or national level cannot be attained if language users cannot and do not use language to avoid conflict. Conflict situations are detrimental to national integration and can lead to underdevelopment. Therefore to avoid these conflict situations the researcher looked at ‘how’ language can be used to avoid conflict and how it can be used for national integration. In order to do justice to the topic, political speeches were selected in the Saturday Vanguard and Daily Sun newspapers to show a negation of the ‘howness’ of language. The theory of verbal hygiene by Deborah Cameron 1995, formed the theoretical framework. This theory which looks at how language can be used in communication in order to impose order on the social world proffered solution to linguistic altercation, verbiage and antagonism that emanate from inappropriate use of language in politics. Three research questions were formulated and the theory of verbal hygiene helped in carrying out its analysis. At the end of the analysis conclusions were drawn and recommendations made.

Keywords: Language, communication “howness” verbal hygiene integration and National integration,

Introduction

One unique quality of the human being is his ability to possess language. Where ever humans exist, language exist. It is “the major distinguishing characteristics between humans and other creatures” (Babajide: 1) Humans are the only creature that use words. He is a “talking being”. Humans think and express themselves in language. According to Adandimeji “mere words, that language produces can make and prevent wars, create understanding or inflame prejudice, form constitutions or destroy them, justify man’s worst actions or express his highest ideas (2).

Language is inevitable to humans because through it, they are able to communicate with other people in the society, share ideas and feelings with others and pass these ideas to succeeding generation (Adetugbo in Nzeakor 141). Language is a unique, powerful instrument for peace, unity and national integration if properly used but if otherwise, it can also lead to disunity, powerlessness and disintegration. That is to say that language is a two edged sword.

Human always neglect the proper use of language because majority of language users are not aware that there is a difference between having a language and performing with a language in actual practical situation. Linguist like Chomsky recognized these differences and hence his introduction of linguistic competence and linguistic performance. Linguistic

competence according to him is the sum total of the knowledge that a native speaker has about his language while communicative competence refers to the ability of a language user to put the knowledge he has about his language in actual communication situation. De Saussure talks about langue and parole, where langue is seen as language, that is, all the rules and conventions regarding the combinations of sounds, formation of words and sentences, pronunciation and meaning. All these conventions constitute langue and are product of social agreement. That is, there is similarity of sounds, words and meaning among the native speakers of a language which means that they have the same images and signs in their minds (qtd. In Pushpinder et al 47).

Langue is also abstract, as these particular conventions exist in the minds of the speakers who belong to that society that have created the language. This is also referred to as the “Whatness” of language, the content of language.

Parole, belongs to the individual. When those conventions that exist in the langue are used in concrete form in actual speech or writing, they become instances of Parole. Parole is individual performance of language in speech or writing. It is concrete and physical. It makes use of the physiological mechanism such as speech organs in uttering words and sentences.

This is referred to as the ‘howness’ of language. It is at this level that human can use language either to integrate or disintegrate.

Integration which is an act of combining two or more things so that they work together or the act or process of mixing people who have been previously separated, usually because of colour, race, religion and so on. Then, national integration refers to those characteristics and beliefs which Nigerians share in common and which bind them together and distinguish them from others. Nigeria as a multi-lingual, multicultural and multiethnic country need proper use of language – be it Hausa, Igbo, Yoruba or English language to keep them together. The problem of disintegration in Nigeria is not bordered on language but on the “howness” of language use, that is, how Nigerian people especially politicians use language to tarnish the image of others.

This paper therefore advocates the use of verbal Hygiene which will enable communicators to be selective and careful in their use of language to avoid conflict situations which is detrimental to national integration. The theory of verbal Hygiene by Deborah Cameron published in 1995 formed the theoretical framework under which this work was carried out.

Conceptual Framework

Language as a Concept

The concept of language has attracted a lot of definitions from both linguists and non linguists alike and each has tried to define the concept to reflect his/her area of specialization. Some of these definitions will be looked into.

According to Hornby in Okpara, language is “the system of sounds and words used by humans to express their thoughts and feelings” (260). It connotes characteristic ways of talking, thinking and feeling about attitude, goals and ideas. Emenanjo on his own definition sees language as a particular way or style of speaking or writing. It is that complete whole of communication which includes signs, symbols, knowledge belief and customs and cultures and any other abilities of speech acquired by mankind for the sole purpose of communication and identity (Hornby in Okpara 260). Language here is seen as the total configuration of a Person or group of persons that enables people in the society share common information and ideas.

The Encyclopedia Americana International Education 2000 edition, volume 16, defines language as the principle and richest means of communication used by human being. “It functions primarily as a spoken means of communication” (19). This definition excludes non-verbal language use. Nevertheless, language as a system of communication is one of the biological characteristics that distinguish humans from other animals, birds, insects etc.

All human communities possess language, thus it is perhaps the single most significant property that distinguish human from other animals. Just as all living creature depend on water and earth around us so, also the society depends on language for its existence.

According to Fromkin, Rodman and Hymes, language is defined thus:

We live in a world of language, we talk to our friends, our lovers, our teachers, our parents, our rivals and even our enemies. We talk to bus drivers and total strangers, we talk face to face and over telephone and everyone responds with more talk. Television and radio further swell this torrent of words. Hardly a moment of our waking lives is from words (284).

From the above explanation of language, everybody uses language and language is used to perform varieties of functions, but there is also an exclusion of the non-verbal aspect of language use.

Again, Fromkin, Rodman and Hymes while still answering the question – what is language? Explain that, “it is whatever people may do when they play, fight. Make love or make automobiles”. They however conclude by asserting that we are the animals that do this – talk (1). This definition includes both verbal, non-verbal etc. That is to say, that the totality of human activities are language based.

Communication

Communication can be defined as a quality of being able to communicate, that is, to give or pass on information, feelings, diseases etc. Effective communication can be attained only when language is properly used both linguistically and para-linguistically and these are what linguists refer to as linguistic and communicative competences. The knowledge of only the linguistic features of a language cannot make one communicate effectively but one has to look at other para-linguistic features that are involved in communication.

According to Ngonebu, communication is transmission of information from one person to another in order to elicit a response (56). Ijeoma defines communication as an interaction by means of signs and symbols. The symbols may be gesture, picture, plastic or verbal or any other which would serve as stimuli to behaviour (213).

In the words of Eyre in (Sybil et al 3), communication is not just the giving of information, it is the giving of understandable information and receiving and understanding the message. Communication is the transferring of a message to another party so that it can be understood and acted upon.

Communication touches every sphere of human activity. It informs all of man’s actions because it is occasioned by his need to interact with his fellow human. It manifests itself in

symbolic, verbal forms. Animals and trees also communicate, but it is man's ability to create symbols, ascribe meanings and interpret messages that elevates him above the status of lower animals and gives form and character to his existence (Sybil, Isaac O. Oludayos 1)

Communication also serves as an instrument of social interaction. It helps us to understand ourselves, to keep in touch with other people, to understand them and to predict their response to situations. It is a means by which power is acquired, exercised and sustained. It is the medium through which people in business, politics and the professions act, and interact, exchange information and ideas, develop plans, proposals and policies, make decisions and manage men/women and materials.

Furthermore, communication is the interaction in one form or the other, either by visual or auditory symbols. People are continually interacting with themselves and with their environment by talking to their friends, watching television, listening to the radio, reading printed pages, calling or sending away domestic or other animals. Communication involves the interaction of one or more people saying or doing something which attracts reactions in the minds of other people. Symbols such as words or gestures are the major means that people use to communicate.

Similarly, communication can also be defined as the transmission, transfer or exchange of ideas, knowledge, beliefs or attitudes from one person to another. Communication is thus a process by which we assign and convey meaning in an attempt to create shared understanding. This process requires a vast repertoire of skills in intrapersonal and interpersonal processing, listening, observing, speaking, questioning, analyzing and evaluating. Ginibo (20) defines communication as the process of using verbal and non-verbal cues to transact mutually understood meanings between two or more people within a particular context and environment.

Dopemu (10), defined communication as a process by which one person (or a group) shares and imparts information to another (or group) and which information is clearly understood by one another. Communication is the act of transferring or conveying information from a human source to a signaling system.

In a nutshell, communication is not just giving of information, it is the giving of understandable information and receiving understandable message by different parties so that such message can be understood and acted upon.

Components of Communication

Communication process is made up of five components, these are:

- **Sender/Encoder:** The sender is the fellow who encodes the message. He/she is the source or originator of the message. i.
- **Receiver/Decoder:** The receiver is the one that decodes the message, that is, he interprets the message. He/she is the target audience and the final consumer of the communication. ii.
- **Message:** Message or meanings reside in receivers and not in messages. The sender sends an array of messages from which each receiver selects an array of messages from which each receiver selects the message or parts of the message which maintain and enhance his own organizational structure. The message is the content, idea, thoughts and information the sender/source wishes to share with the receiver, listener. This is the central element in the communication process. iii.
- **Medium:** This is the channel or network of channels connecting the sender or receiver. In communication process, the channel helps to shape the message.
- **Feedback:** The feedback is the response by the receiver to the message transmitted. Feedback in the communication process can be positive or negative. It is the reaction on the part of the receiver as a result of the reception of the message.
- **Noise:** Noise is an interference that affects the effectiveness of a communication activity. Noise reduces and affects the quality of the message at any stage of the communication process.
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Types of Communication

There are three types of communication

i. Dialogue or verbal communication

ii. Non verbal communication

Visual communication.

Dialogue or Verbal Communication: It is a reciprocal conversation between two or more entities. This is communication through the use of words. It may take oral form in which speech organs are used to produce sounds or written form in which human muscles are used to write symbols letters of the alphabet and words.

Non Verbal Communication: Non verbal communication is the process of communicating through sending and receiving wordless messages. Such message can be communicated through gesture, body language or posture, facial expressions and eye contacts, object communication such as clothing, hairstyles or even symbols or information graphics. Speech may also contain non verbal elements known as paralanguage, including voice quality, emotion and speaking style, as well as prosodic features such as rhythm, interaction and stress.

Visual Communication: Visual communication through aid. It is the conveyance of ideas and information in forms that can be read or looked upon. It is primarily associated with dimensional images. It includes signs, typography, drawing, graphic design,

illustration, colour and electronic resources. It solely relies on vision.

Characteristics of Effective Communication

Some of the major characteristics of effective communication are:

Directional: Effective communication should be directed towards a definite population or class

Purposeful: It should have a definite objective. It should be aimed at achieving a purpose.

Meaningful: It must be intelligibly encoded in symbols that are commonly understood and easily interpreted by all concerned.

Systemic: There should normally be a link between one idea or component and another. The idea and expressions must function co-operatively to achieve a common goal.

The roles of Effective Communication

The roles of effective communication are:

- It prevents unnecessary speculation and rumour
- Effective communication enhances harmonious relationship among the different units or organization.
- It may prevent the breakdown of law and order in an organisation as rumour and speculation have been reduced to the barest minimum through regular and efficient communication
- Regular and efficient communication will no doubt lead to the achievement of organizational goals.

In conclusion, communication is an issue that cannot be joked with as it is the means of

interaction and transmission of information between people. Therefore, any breakdown in communication is enough to lead to anarchy, confusion and rumours. The above brief consideration of communication emphasizes its importance in human interaction. Thus no institution can survive without communication and no integration can go on without effective communication which entails the ‘how’ of language. As humans our language use should be such that rancor, conflict and animosity should be avoided. Communication is a very important concept in human integration and language provides the mental and physical apparatus for rapid, social and national integration and more in our conceptual views of hu

Howness of Language

“Howness” of language as a means towards national integration

The above tree diagram explains the ‘howness’ of language use. The ‘howness’ of language is the form, the manner, the style, the how, the medium through which language plays out the role assigned to it. It is truism

that every normal human being possesses language but the reason why some writers or speakers are tagged good and others bad. 'Howness' takes cognizance of context of situation in arriving at a particular message.

It is not so much interested in the content, the theme, the subject matter, the message and the what of a language. It pays particular attention on the effect a language will have on its interlocutors. Man/woman existence and exchange of ideas, culture and technology.

The concept of Verbal Hygiene

Verbal hygiene is a concept that denotes the use of politically, socially, religiously and linguistically correct words to express our opinions, ideas and views in a given situation. The concept of verbal hygiene is a new area of sociolinguistics, pragmatics and discourse analysis study coined by a British linguist Deborah Cameron to create awareness on the use of language which is culturally, socially and linguistically correct. Certainly, language involves producing and sending information which is often decoded by an individual through the mechanism of his social context. Verbal hygiene does not mean that speakers should be economical with the truth but can express our opinion respectively without causing unnecessary frictions in the society. Cameron Deborah argues that language use is paradigmatically a social and public act, therefore, talking, writing and

signing must be carried out with reference to norms which may themselves become the subject of overt comment and debate.

Research Questions

Three research questions were formulated which helped in proffering answers to the research problems. These research questions are:

- 1) To what extent do language use in politics cause/lead to national integration?
- 2) What effect has verbal hygiene on language use?
- 3) What roles can communicators play in bringing about national integration through their language use in politics?

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Verbal Hygiene

Verbal hygiene is a term coined by sociolinguist Deborah Cameron in the first edition of her book, published in 1995. Cameron (2012) defines it as the "Motley collection of discourses and practices through which people attempt to 'clean up' language and make its structure or its use conform more closely to their ideals of beauty, truth, efficiency, logic, correctness and civility central to Cameron's discussion is the idea that, behind the ostensible desire to regulate language and ensure standards, verbal hygiene practices hide a range of deeper social, moral and political anxieties.

Verbal hygiene practices, argues Cameron, are inevitable and common to all language users.

Whether these practices are carried out to criticize deviant or incorrect language forms and to impose standard, or to argue against any form of interference with ‘natural’ changes, both linguists and lay people have strong ideas about how a specific language should sound, work and look.

“Our norms and values differ” argues Cameron, but “what remains constant is that we have norms and values” (9). This ‘urge to meddle in matters of language’ is a consequence of the fact that humans do not just use language, but also observe and reflect on the language they use. Linguists may engage in verbal hygiene practices to prescribe how language should work or to describe how it works. In both cases, however, they are engaging in struggle to control language by defining its nature as either a man-made product to be controlled or natural entity to be observed.

Verbal hygiene according to Deborah is concerned with who has the right to impose specific standards and why, what the language we speak reveals, about us, and how it contributes to shape our identity, which linguistic changes are acceptable and which are to be discouraged (and why) are all questions.

The Concepts of Integration and National Integration

The term “integration” refers to a process whereby the quality of relations among

autonomous social units (kingship groups, tribes, cities, trade unions, trade associations, political parties) change in such a way as to erode the autonomy of each and make it part of a larger aggregate (encyclopedia.com). It is also defined as mixing things or people together that were formerly separated. It is the bringing of different racial or ethnic groups into free and equal association www.yourdictionary.com.

The aim of integration is to maintain a harmonious and active relationship between the various structural components of society. It is not only keeping the society going but also impacts a meaning and purpose to the lives of individuals so that they feel to be of a comprehensible and harmonious social life. Integration therefore organizes and harmonizes the institutions, organizations and other structural forms so that they operate together to serve the purposes of society and to develop orderly social entity.

Modes of Integration

Societies are integrated in different ways. In totalitarian societies the government controls social life so completely that each structural form is completely co-ordinated with the aims these societies support. Thus, in communities, societies, the schools, the churches, economic agencies, organizations and all manifestations of collective behaviour are subsumed under the policies and controls of the government. There is only one political party, and it

controls all other organizations including families. It controls all communication channels. The activities of each agency are directed through its official hierarchy. No challenge to its power or the system of values that defines its aims are tolerated. It achieves its integration by threat or use of force, such a mode of integration has been called “closely woven” type of integration.

On the other hand there are “loosely woven” societies. In such societies, there is a variation not only in individual behaviour but also in nations behaviour. It does not, however, mean that the society is not integrated or poorly integrated. It only implies that there are no rigid social norms and that people have a wide range of alternative modes of behaviour open to them. The group relationships are not well-defined and the moral norms are laxly carried out, ours is a loosely woven society. In order to remove the strain towards anomie and to keep the society on-going integration is persistently sought. Generally speaking, people carry their activities in a normative fashion. There is general support for the folkways, mores and institutional patterns. However, beyond the daily reinforcement integration by normative behaviour, deliberate efforts are also made for bringing about social integration. Thus ameliorative programmes are carried out to decrease delinquency, to educate voters, to provide help to the under privilege and the over burdened and to improve education, housing, medical care, recreation and local

administration. These programmes select to make improvements in the existing structural forms without fundamentally affecting the basic pattern of social structure.

From the above, understanding of integration involves people from different ethnic background coming together for a harmonious living. This cannot be achieved without appropriate language use for effective communication. Language oils the social relationship of a society so the way and manner it is applied in every context is bound to mar or foster integration. Positive enhancement of integration in politics through language usage is the crux of this paper.

National integration, otherwise termed nation-building loyalty, national unity, national cohesion, national loyalty, or the national question “involves consensus on the limits of the political community and on the nature of the political regime” Liddle 205 cited on Otite: 188). This simply means the forging of agreement among the members of a state on the extent of unity they wish to have as well as the type of political structure and institutions city, based on an order its members regard as equitably harmonious city, based on an order its members regard as equitably harmonious” (Duverger:177). This implies that integration promotes unity which encourages smooth interaction among the member of the given

society based on certain established principles of fairness.

Jacob and Tenue (9) define national integration as “relationship of community among people within the same political entity... state of mind or disposition to be cohesive, to act together, to be committed to mutual programmes”. They are thus referring to a society of oneness whose members are willing to live and work together harmoniously and share the same destiny. It has also been viewed as:

a process by which members of a social system develop linkages so that the boundaries of the system persists over time and the boundaries of sub-systems become less consequential in affecting behavior. In this process, members of the social system develop an escalating sequence of contact, cooperation, consensus and community (Morrison et al, 385 cited in Ojo,:51).

This relates to a situation where territorial divisions within a polity gradually yield ground to cordial interactions of its members owing to the integrative mechanisms established. From the above explanations of integration and national integration, Nigerian politics have a question to answer – are they really integrated?

Empirical Studies

A lot of works had been written on effective language use for communication and conflicts resolution. Two of such works will be cited

here to authenticate the work. A research work written by Nzeakor & Osondu titled “Language and Effective Communication best practice for change management” looked at how effective language can lead to positive change. The communication accommodation theory by Howard Giles propounded in 1991 was used as the theoretical framework. Some conversations from Adichie’s work *Half of a Yellow Sun* were randomly selected to do justice to the work. At the end of the analysis of these conversations, the researchers discovered that change can be positively or negatively reached depending on how effective our language is. For positive change, communicators who accommodated their communication partners convergently got it while negative change came from those who could not accommodate their communication partners (divergently). The researchers therefore conclude that for there to be positive change, and for change to be effectively managed, communicators should equip themselves with all the linguistic nuisances like being communicatively competent which include grammatical competences, which will enable the communicator to have a strong hold of his/her listeners which in turn enable them to co-operate. It is this co-operation that leads to positive change and management.

Again in another work by the same writers titled “Accommodation Principles as Strategies for conflict resolutions. A study of *Purple Hibiscus* by Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie looked at how language can be used for conflict

resolutions. They used accommodation theory which was propounded by Howard Giles in 1991 to understudy their work. This theory based on two Principles of convergence and divergence helped the researchers to do a proper analysis of the work. In their findings they discovered that convergence behaviour in language use leads to politeness and co-operation while divergence behaviour causes disagreement, non-co-operation and conflict and in extreme cases death. In conclusion, they recommend that communicators should look out for linguistic signs that can make their communicants co-operate with them so as to avoid conflicting situations.

Analysis of some Selected Political Speeches in some Nigerian Newspapers to show a negation of the 'Howness' of Language

Except 1: Why should you sue Mr. President to context re-election?

The question already indicates a soiled relationship. This is a state of compulsion – whether the president likes it or not 'He' must context for a re-election. This question was asked as a result of a statement made by Governor Abdulahi Gauduje, "when he came to Kano, I told him that any time he decides not to context, we will take him to court. Kano state government will take him to court any time he decides not to context. So we are waiting for him" (13). Another example from the same Newspaper has this to say: "In the same vein, another ardent supporter of Mr. President's re-

election bid, Governor Yahaya Belo of Kogi state insists that President must accept to run". (13) The use of must indicates compulsion which can cause conflict and disintegration. Such language should be avoided.

Except II: Cross River: The Storm is not over (10)

From this caption, there is already an existing problem/trouble and the effect will yield a negative result which can mare national integration. It continues: "There has never been any love lost between the self acclaimed 'original' members of the All Progressives Congress, APC, and the new entrants into the party from the People's Democratic Party, PDP, since after 2015 general elections in Cross River State. They had always operated in parallel without pretence" (Saturday Vanguard 10).

From the above statement, we see a state of anarchy, disorderliness and hatred between Nigerians that belonged to different political parties. How can National integration be achieved through this means? There is this common aphorism that says "united we stand" but "divided we fall" Nigerians cannot achieve national integration under a state of division in political parties. This can be achieved through verbal hygiene, that is, being mindful of the words we use

Except III Oyo: The return of trouble (Saturday Vanguard 11)

This caption is an indication of a troubled state. In such a state, there will be disunity, rancor, and disintegration. In furtherance of the disintegration in this state we have this: “The Lamists see Governor Ajimobi as a “Supplanter” who came from the All Nigerian People’s Party to reap the harvest of their years of labour in the former Action Congress of Nigeria, CAN”.

There is name calling in this excerpt. The resultant effect is what we have here.

It was as such not surprising when hell was let loose last Saturday when the Pacesetter state once, again, witnessed another political turmoil as supporters of one of the factions threw caution to the wind... When the dust settled, it left tales of pains and injuries. Two members of the committee set up to ... sustained injuries (Saturday Vanguard 11).

Except IV: APC driving Nigeria to anarchy – PDP (National news 10)

This open quotation has already established a state of anarchy in Nigeria. Furthermore, on the use of harsh language we see this: “It is clear that the APC is not organic but a Souless mob, without any form of conscience and integrity, an evil wind that blows no good”.

Again we see also in this quotation below another language that can cause serious harm to National integration. “APC has become a symbol and harbinger of malevolence, which by every indication is on a sordid throttle of taking out nation to the long-forgotten state of nature when only the might rules; the state of anarchy” (10).

From all the statements and analysis done, we can observe that, the language of politics is not favourable to National integration rather is leads to conflict, violence, disintegration and in extreme cases death. This is as a result of politicians not knowing the difference between the ‘howness’ and the ‘whatness’ of language use. In order to avoid these conflict situations, Cameron’s verbal hygiene theory should be adopted.

Conclusion

The importance of using respectful, unbiased and effective language is fundamental towards achieving long lasting peace, unity which can lead to national integration. All hands must be on deck in order to achieve this in Nigerian politics. Our everyday use of word must show love for one another. Nigerian politicians must maximize the importance of our multilingual nature as a strength rather than weakness because we have gone a long way as a nation.

This paper have been able to prove that verbal hygiene is an important decisive factor of civilization and the instrument of achieving national unity and peace which can lead to national integration. Good use of language devoid of inciting and dehumanizing words is the mechanism through which every human society is destroyed or transformed.

This paper argued that the ultimate solution to ethnic, religious, political conflicts hampering integration in Nigeria lies in sincere attitudinal

change as it regards our use of words to express our sentiments, views and opinions.

To this end, our leaders and indeed every Nigerian must show love, respect and politeness in their utterances. With this type of attitudinal change conflicts will be averted and socio political violence will be a thing of the past and Nigeria will speak with one voice. This is the time to achieve this oneness, love and unity for integration to take place.

Recommendations

1. Every user of language whether English or any other language should strive to use language consciously to achieve mutual understanding and peaceful co-existence through our use of words to relate with one another. Effective communication begin with caring about the feeling of other receiver of your message. You must care about the people with whom you will be communicating about and what will happen as a result of your communication. As such you must be objective and factual in what you are writing or talking about.
2. Teachers of language should as a matter of urgency begin to inculcate in the studies of linguistic attitudes of talking to people politely and respectfully especially when we do not share these opinions and when we tend to disagree with them.
3. Parents also should be mindful of how they speak to their child because children live by what they see.

4. Hate speeches should be around by our leaders
5. Mass media should inform and educate the general public with truthful information.
6. Seminars on good language use should be organized for our politicians to enable them to know the 'howness' of a language use which help in fostering national integration.

References

- Babajide, A.O. (ed) *Studies in English Language* (Pp. 168-187). Ibadan: Enigrownit publishers.
- Dopemu, E.A. et al *Language and Communication Skills for Schools and Colleges*. Kano: Flash printers. (2010).
- Duverger, Maurice (1976) *The study of politics*. Hong Kong. Nelson Political Science library
- Fromkin, V.B. Rodman & N. Hymes. *An Introduction to Language* (8th ed) USA: Thomas Wardsworth (2007).
- Ginibo, E.O. What is communication? *The Definition of Communication* <http://www.communicationstudies.com/whatis-communication>. (2012).
- Ijeoma, C.P. *Communication, Language and the arts Readings in African Humanities. African Perspectives in Egonu* (ed) world culture Owerri: Vivians and Vivians publishers (1988).
- Liddle, R.W. *Ethnicity, Party and national integration: An Indonesian case study*. New Haven: Yale University press. (1970).
- Morrison, Donald G, et al *Black Africa: A Comparative Handbook*. New York: The Free Press. (1972).
- Nzeakor Ngozi C. & Nnadi Ogechi, A. *Human Language and communication: Prospects and Problems*. In *issues in Language and Human development: A Festschrift for Jerome Ikechukwu Okonkwo*. (Ed) Polycarp A. Anyanwu & Ifeoma Obuasi. Enugu: San Press Ltd. (2012).

Nzeakor, N.C. & Patience Osundu. Accommodation Principles as strategies for conflict resolution. A study of Purple Hibiscus by Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie. Unpublished paper.

_____ Language and Effective communication best practice for change management. A study of Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun*. Unpublished Seminar paper.

Okpara Chika. Language and Culture as Conflict Resolution Tools: Rethinking English as Lingua Franca. In issues in Language and Human development: A Festschrift for Jerome Ikechukwu Okonkwo. Ed-Polycarp A. Anyanwu & Ifeoma Obuasi Enugu: San Press Ltd. (2012).

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